

Management

FAITH TOURISM IN TAGAYTAY CITY: BASIS FOR DESTINATION MARKETING

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Abstract

A Faith Tourism tour package was proposed in one of the prominent cities in the Province of Cavite, Philippines based on Dr. Sampad Kumar Swain's basic tour package components. Through Focus Group Discussion, document analysis and survey questionnaire, the study determined eight tour operators and their clients' knowledge of Faith Tourism including its benefits and opportunities, and the skills and attitudes in making a Faith Tourism tour package. SWOT Analysis determined the marketing competitiveness of Tagaytay City through the World Economic Forum's Tourism and Travel Competitive Index (TTCI) 2017. The millennial respondents of the survey questionnaire strongly agreed that the proposed faith tourism tour package is competitive and reflects Swain's basic components. The common knowledge among tour operators regarding Faith Tourism is it is a pilgrimage, while the basic skills and attitude needed in making Faith Tourism itineraries are professionalism, knowledgeability, and patience. SWOT analysis as a tool for self-assessment revealed that Tagaytay City is "strongly" competitive based on the TTCI 2017 components.

Keywords: Destination Marketing; Faith Tourism; Tagaytay City; Tour Package.

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1. Introduction

Rieger and Salvatierra (2015) pointed that different types of tourism nowadays have developed. When the faith is considered as an important and primary element in a journey, travel, tour or trip, this is Faith Tourism. The Philippines is a religious country and there are Christians, Islam, Buddhists, however it is evident that the Roman Catholic in the Philippines is the most promoted religious culture which is shown in print and visual media such as different fiestas, Lenten rituals and Christmas celebrations. Any region that has religious celebrations become not just a tourist destination, but a religious destination. Travellers get to witness the religious culture as well as, admire the beauty of some religious infrastructures in a particular area, i.e. major religious

buildings, objects or monuments which are binded to a significant religious and historical events or religious traditions. Even if there is no significant event to celebrate, the traveling faithful still come and visit several religious sites through Pilgrimages. Pilgrimages, as well as all kinds of religious visits are made to see first-hand specific churches, cathedrals and shrines. Visiting these places during a scheduled celebration is an added attraction to the tour. For non-believers, these places are visited not for their religious significance, but for its cultural or historical significance as well.

Capone (2015) said that people travel for a reason and through these reasons, different dimensions of tourism are generated, classified or clustered. Hennighausen (2015) cited heritage tourism, cultural tourism, sports tourism, casino tourism, as examples. McIntosh, Goeldner and Ritchie (2011) enumerated different Motivation Typology on people's participation in tourist and leisure activities where one of which is spiritual reasons. With the many types of tourism, competitiveness in tourism is observable as what Crouch and Ritchie (2012) presented in the challenges of managing, maintaining and enhancing competitive tourism destinations. They said that standardized tour packages is a concrete and early example of tourism competitiveness. Thanks to Olsen and Timothy (2006) and Norman (2013) where they argued that religion and spirituality are still among the most common motivations for travel paving the way for the concept of Faith Tourism. Bryant (2013), Benson (2014), Shepherd (2013) and Shedneck (2015) presented their works on Faith Tourism in other countries particularly in the United States, South-western Nigeria, and in their Asian studies on how in China and Thailand apply western heritage management.

Faith Tourism covers a wide range of attractions and encounters featuring churches, chapels, denominations, architecture, genealogy and pilgrimages. Faith tourism can make any country stand-out in its tourism competitiveness other that its ecotourism services and products. Robledo (2015) reflected and explored this dimension of tourism where the person's outer search of faith is the vehicle for an inner journey of spiritual development in the journey. Visiting the Philippines by both local and foreign tourists under this motivation and purpose will not be a problem for the country have already been promoting Faith Tourism ever since. There are many destinations in different provinces in the Philippines tourists can visit. The Philippine Statistics Authority (2017), released on July 4, 2017 the result of their Home Survey on Domestic Visitors where it revealed the top provinces visited, namely cities of the provinces of Laguna, Cavite, Rizal, Bulacan, Batangas, Benguet, Zambales. Pangasinan and Quezon. Furthermore, it also surveyed the visitor's main purpose of visit where the study said that six (6) percent went because of religion or pilgrimage trip.

The Department of Tourism of the country has an official slogan "It's more fun in the Philippines!". With the advent of Faith Tourism, this slogan may be revised and can become, "It's more spiritually fun in the Philippines!". The Philippines is not just known from its natural and cultural sights and attraction, but also from religious destinations all year round. There was a Regional Department of Tourism who produced a promotional tourism video for its own Region. The video highlighted different destinations that tourists can visit in the five provinces in Region 4-A where the province of Cavite belong. After enumerating the different destinations showed in the video, Cavite was extremely distinct from the other Provinces in Region 4-A in the absence of prominent churches. All other provinces showed and featured elements of Faith Tourism except Cavite. Because of this particular circumstance, the study explored and tried to find out the

possibility of stimulating Faith Tourism in Cavite and since Cavite's Tagaytay City was the best highlighted location in the video, a Faith Tourism Tour Package in Tagaytay City was proposed. The study also finds out what is the perception of different operators and their clients from the proposed Faith tour package based on Dr. Sampad Kumar Swain's basic components of a package tour. Also, the study determined the respondents' perception on the following: first, the knowledge, skills and attitudes in making a Faith Tour package; second, the benefits and opportunities in promoting Faith Tourism; and third, their over-all perception of the tour product based on the TCCI 2017.

The study centered on the preparation of a proposed Faith Tourism Tour Package that is based from Swain's (2017) basic components of a Tour Package. The featured destination for the proposed tour package was Tagaytay City because, other the video concern mentioned earlier, Tagaytay City has the most tourist arrivals in the Province of Cavite based on the report published by the Provincial Tourism Office in 2016. The study used the Input-Process-Output model as conceptual framework. The Input part is the proposed Faith Tourism tour package of Tagaytay City based on the five basis or components of travel according to Dr. Swain, the Process part is the results from the Focus Group Discussion (FGD), Survey Questionnaire and SWOT Analysis, and the Output part is the competitive Faith Tour Package in Tagaytay City.

A brochure was prepared in the study showing Dr. Sampad Kumar Swain's five basic components of a package tour which are Tourist Attractions, Tourist Destination, Transportation, Meals and accommodation, and Tourist activities. The study is valuable and useful to local tourism, religious and education sector. In the local scenario, the Philippines has been a breathtaking meeting point among international tourists and a pride among the local tourists. Tourists visit and travel the Philippines because of the many kinds of tourism the country offers, Faith Tourism is one of them. The proposed Faith Tourism Travel package in Tagaytay City can be used as model by local tourism, particularly the different travel agencies to further progress the present tourism competitiveness of the country. In the religious and education sector, the proposed tour package has tour destinations highlighting seminaries, sacred and spiritual places of Tagaytay City. Visiting these destinations and participating in its lined-up activities are beneficial in the promotion and deepening of one's faith. The inclusion, discussion and promotion of Faith Tourism as an added Information in education will enrich and will give more value among teachers and students on the goals and rationale of required educational tours.

2. Materials and Methods

The study, in general, is categorized under the field of Educational Research where scientific and systematic approaches in research are applied to the study of educational problems, educational research is the result. Most educational research undertakings follow Qualitative Inquiry, however in order to determine the basis for competitiveness of the proposed Faith Tourism Tour Package of Tagaytay City, the study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches.

On the use of qualitative approach, Creswell (2012), defined qualitative research as an inquiry process of understanding based on distinct methodological traditions of inquiry that explore a social or main problem. Technically, Creswell has laid conditions for a qualitative research to be called such like the use of FGD in which this study on Faith Tourism is correlative. The FGD

focused on the knowledge, skills and attitudes towards making Faith Tourism itineraries, as well as the opportunities and benefits and over-all perception of the tour product based on the Travel and Tourism Competitive Index (TTCI) 2017.

On the use of quantitative approach, Dwyer, Gill and Seeteram (2012) enumerated examples or methodologies and approaches under Quantitative Researches. From the many Quantitative Research approaches enumerated, one was used in the study, specifically the statistical testing techniques. The statistical testing technique was used to treat the data gathered through the validated survey questionnaire by a statistician. From the frequencies, weighed means, the statistician also mathematically interpreted the obtained questionnaire.

After the FGD, all tour operators that attended were requested by the researchers to accomplish on her behalf the survey questionnaire to their walk-in clients. The instrument is a 25-item self-made questionnaire and it was based on the five basis or components of travel according to Dr. Swain. The competitiveness of Tagaytay City was assessed using SWOT analysis in the light of TTCI 2017. The Output part, based on recorded proceedings of the FGD and the treated results of the questionnaire, presented a revised and competitive Faith Tourism Tour Package in Tagaytay City which can be used as a model example for other Faith Tourism package in the country.

The data of the study was provided by different tour operators or travel agents and their clients. Specifically, these data came from the recorded and documented proceedings in the travel agent's FGD, as well as, the data coming from the accomplished survey questionnaire by the travel agents' respective clients. The twenty-five item, validated self-made questionnaire was based on Swain's five basic components that a package tour must have, namely: tourist attractions, tourist destination, transportation, meals and accommodation, and tourist activities.

Permission letters were prepared addressed to the Provincial Tourism Officer, Tagaytay City Tourism Officer, and the President of Cavite Travel and Tours Association (CTTA). The approval, recommendation and endorsement from the two tourism officers were sought as a courtesy and respect to the nature of their offices in relation to the study on Faith Tourism in the province. The President of CTTA was also formally sought permission and approval with the hope that its endorsement will make the associations' Travel Agency members to attend and participate in an FGD-seminar.

The seminar component was added by the researchers to encourage more participants and show the study's Educational Research component. The proposed Faith Tourism Tour package brochure was the highlight in the FGD and after the FGD, the survey questionnaire was distributed to the Travel Agencies who attended with a gentle request for their clients to answer and accomplish regarding the proposed Tour Package. After the FGD-seminar, the eight Travel Agencies who attended and participated were given each ten (10) survey questionnaires for their walk-in clients to answer. From the total of eighty (80) survey questionnaires distributed, the researchers were able to retrieved sixty-one (61) questionnaires.

3. Results and Discussions

Demographics

These are the demographic profile of the study based on age, gender, marital status and educational attainment. According to Si (2017), the CEO and founder of search engine optimization (SEO) Hacker and Qeryz, demographic questions in the demographic profile allow a person to know who the research target market really is and what they are really thinking of. The target market to answer the survey questionnaire were the different clients of tour operators who participated in the focus group discussion, thus, describing the demographics of the study, the research partners or respondents who answered the questionnaire were clients who belong to the young and single generation who are mostly male in their college level, a typical millennial.

Based on the age interval who answered the survey questionnaire, overwhelming majority are from ages 18-27. While those who belong to the 58-67 age interval was the lowest. These results and findings clearly proved the study made by Expedia Inc (2013) where the study established the Millennials who have more travel opportunities than older peers. The age interval used by Expedia Inc (2013) were 30 and under, 31-45 years old, and 46-65 years old, however they described the millennials as those between 18 to 30. The study used a 10-year interval beginning with age 18 years old. Comparing the rate of travel between the 18-27 and 58-67 age groups, Rabin (2014) expressed that this [millennials] age group is beginning to outpace the baby boomers since millennials travel frequently, are tech-savvy, and are able to travel with ease due to the abundance of free information online. The results proved that Rabin was right.

The male respondents dominated the female with a 54.1 to 45.9 percent ratio. Although the difference between the number of male respondents and the women is slight, the data still show the dominance male over the female, however not that immense. In Rabin's study, she admitted the male dominated environment in most societies, and this social condition makes woman to stay in their homes restricting their leisure activities, thus its mostly the men who travel more compared to the women. However, the data above does not give a significant generalization because the difference of the percentages are of small amount. This result instead supports another finding of Rabin that women in the late twentieth century are no longer the underprivileged gender. There is still a difference though, but not significantly dominating.

As to the marital status, the single ones with a frequency of 46 were the majority who answered, which means they managed to have the time to visit a tour operator and answer the 25-item survey questionnaire. The married clients of tour operators followed next with a frequency of 14. One widower answered the questionnaire, too. Bianchi (2016) observed that a growing number of people are travelling alone which reflects why the majority who answered the survey questionnaire were single. However, upon talking to some tour operators in some constant follow-ups, they said that most of them were indeed single or sometimes single couples who went to visit their office mainly to inquire. Some were inquiring a trip for their family, for ticketing since it's the holy week, etc. The study agrees with Bianchi that the trend of travelling alone is rapidly increasing, but the study was interested in coming up with a demographic profile on how many answered the survey questionnaire single in marital status and not how many will travel as solo because a traveller can have a travel buddy and remain single. Bianchi stressed that most single ones are independent,

aggressive, and critical in thinking. The critical in thinking is what this study needed in answering the survey questionnaire.

Among the 61 who answered the survey questionnaire, there was a single client among the tour operators who was a High School graduate; the college level got a frequency of 34; there were 14 college graduates; and the graduate degree got a frequency of 12. The survey questionnaire was administered for two weeks during the Holy Week period where most students have no classes, especially the college ones. It is for this reason why more than half answered the questionnaire where most clients who went to the office were single, and perhaps college teenagers.

Perceptions on the Proposed Faith Tourism Tour Package

On the perception of the respondents from the proposed Faith Tourism Tour package in terms of tourist attraction, the criteria on “Tourist attractions in the itinerary were all associated with Faith Tourism” received the highest weighed mean, while the criteria on “Attractions can be competitive with other forms of tourism (cultural, adventure, etc.)” received the lowest weigh mean. On the over-all perception, the respondents “Strongly Agree” on these three other criteria: “These attractions have religious value and significance”, “The attractions are prominently holy and sacred attractions” and “The religiosity of the tourist attractions that are prominently seen in the travel package”. Adding the most appealing attractions in a package tour sightseeing is one among the most important elements in a package tour. Since Faith Tourism is being promoted, attractions related to Faith Tourism were included. As to its competitiveness, the best of experiences is counted on the kind of sightseeing [tourism] that is conducted, thus one must not forget inclusion of attractions to a package tour that are carefully sequenced in such a manner that the customer satisfaction is enhanced from point to point.

On the perception of the respondents in terms of tourist destination, the criteria on “Tagaytay is a place where you can play, eat, sleep and pray” received the highest weighed mean while the criteria on “The six major tourist destinations are clearly the star in the travel package” received the lowest weigh mean. The respondents “Strongly Agree” on the other criteria namely: “Tagaytay has the resources that can stimulate one’s faith”, “Tagaytay can be a potential Faith Tourism destination” and “Tagaytay can be recommended as a Faith Tourism destination”. Analyzing this result, besides the common “Strongly Agree” interpretation, the weigh mean of each criterion were all extremely high. Tourist destinations indeed is a major product component in tourism because it showed the importance of tourist destination in any proposed tour package. Additionally, the respondents unanimously “strongly agreed” that Tagaytay City is a competitive tourist destination for Faith Tourism.

On the perception of the respondents from the proposed Faith Tourism Tour package in terms of transportation, the criteria on “The travel package has provided options” and the criteria on “The transportation inclusion is clearly seen and explained in the travel package” both received the highest weighed mean, while the criteria on “The transportation in the itinerary is safe and conducive for travel” received the lowest weigh mean. The respondents “Strongly Agree” on the rest of the criteria namely: “The travel package has provided transportation options” and “The transportation inclusion is clearly seen and explained in the travel package” and “Public transportation services can be an accessible option in the itinerary”. In Dr. Swain’s five basic components of an ideal tour package, Transportation is included and the respondents strongly

agreed that travelling is a major part of any tour. Transportation thus indeed is another focal component in a package tour.

On the perception of the respondents from the proposed Faith Tourism Tour package in terms of Meals and accommodation, the criteria on “The accommodation in the itinerary has religious setting” received the highest weighed mean, while the criteria on “The meals and accommodations in the package is clearly seen and explained” received the lowest weigh mean. The respondents “Strongly Agree” on the other criteria namely: “The seminaries and retreat houses are attractive for accommodation”, “The package gives the tourist freedom to choose preferred meal arrangements” and “The itinerary has alternative options for meals and accommodations”. Dr. Swain included meals and accommodation as one of the basic elements of a tour package because when a tourist visits a place and decides to book for an accommodation, meals normally are included. Respondents strongly agreed that the accommodation in the proposed tour package has religious setting and sure enough because these are seminaries and retreat houses. When tourists or visitors’ book for accommodations in a retreat house, meals are automatically included. Booking in retreat houses is not expensive, in fact the published on-line rate for Tagaste Retreat House is 1,000 PhPeso or 20US\$ per person, Light of the World is 1,200 PhPeso or 24US\$. Other seminaries and retreat houses in Tagaytay City were also enumerated in the travel package brochure for reference and information purposes only and tourist will personally make the meal and accommodation arrangements on their own, that is why respondents perceived the criteria on meals and accommodations in the package is clearly seen and explained the least among the five criteria even if the interpretation it received is “Strongly Agree”.

On the perception of the respondents from the proposed Faith Tourism Tour package in terms of tourist activities, the criteria on “The activities will surely provide a meaningful religious experience” received the highest weighed mean, while the criteria on “The activities can be participated by tourists belonging to other faith” received the lowest weigh mean. The respondents “Strongly Agree” on the other criteria namely: “The destinations and attractions have scheduled activities which are organized”, “The activities are clearly seen and explained in the proposed tour package” and “These activities are proper and suitable for Faith tourism”. This result shows that tourist activities are important in a tour package. Dr. Swain even enumerated several tourist activities of Adventure Tour Operators Association of India (ATOAI). The activities of ATOAI members include Trekking, Mountaineering, Bike Tours, Sailing, Ballooning, Hand gliding and Heli-skiing and other Aero Sports, Skiing, Camel / Jeep / Horse Safari, Wildlife Safari, Fishing, Scuba Diving Rafting and other related water sports, Tribal Tours (Swain, 2014). Since the proposed tour package of this study is about Faith Tourism, the different activities are related to Faith Tourism. The respondents “Strongly Agreed” that these activities will surely provide a meaningful religious experience. It is expected however that the criteria on “the activities can be participated by tourists belonging to other faith” will receive the least rating since most tourists who participate in faith tourism are Catholic.

Recalling the importance of demographic questions in a study, Si (2017) said that demographic questions do not only allow the researcher to know who the target market of the study really is, as well as, what they [the market] are really thinking of, the result of what clients think or the perception of clients on the proposed Faith Tourism Tour Package is an overwhelming identical interpreted result. Ranking the five components from highest to lowest, Tourist Destination ranked

first, second was Tourist Attractions, third was Tourist Activities, fourth was Meals and accommodation, and fifth in rank was Transportation. Analyzing this ranking, Tourist destination must rank first from all other components, because according to Dr. Swain, a [tour] package can be categorized by the destinations as it features. Tour package is designed selecting all the components at a single destination. Tourists are taken to that specific destinations and it is experienced to the fullest. Since the tour package is about Faith Tourism, destinations that stir the Faith must be the highlights, which the respondents strongly agreed. What components come with destination, logically these are the destinations' attractions and activities that is why these two were ranked second and third respectively. In the proposed Faith Tourism Tour Package in Tagaytay City brochure, the different scheduled activities and the attractions that made these destinations popular are included which was strongly agreed according to the survey result. The two last components according to rankings does not mean that they are not important, but instead it show what Faith Tourism must prioritize namely destination, attractions and activities, Meals/accommodation and Transportation are not set aside, but are planned after the destination, attractions and activities are first established.

Knowledge in Faith Tourism

During the FGD proper, the participants were made to share their thoughts on their idea about Faith Tourism. The first FGD question was, "what is your idea of "Faith Tourism"? Is this reflective in the proposed Tagaytay Faith-tour package?" Analyzing the responses given, Faith tourism as it was explained in the discussion, is a tour which is same and similar to a pilgrimage. This specific finding that from the FGD totally agrees with Darfoon's (2013) description of Faith tourism, where said that faith tourism or religious tourism, is a pilgrimage that is exclusively or strongly motivated by religious reasons. The proposed tour package offers a tour visit into a lot of religious and historical churches in Tagaytay city. This faith tourism aims to make the tour not just enjoyable but also religious in order to help us strengthen the religion we belong and our faith, as well as our relationship through the Holy creator. Additionally, the participants strongly agreed that the elements of Faith Tourism can be seen on the proposed tour package.

Skills in Making Faith Tourism Itineraries

The second FGD question was, "based on your experience in making tour itineraries, what skill must a travel agent possess in coming up with a Faith-tour package? Is this skill seen in the proposed package?". Chan and Tay (2016) said that training is needed to enhance the staffs' knowledge about sustainability issues, especially for tour guides who bring the tourists along the trip. One participant emphasize that training is provided to front-line staffs because they are the person who communicate to the guests face to face. All the necessary skills were enumerated, however, another thing that was mentioned in the discussion is a tour guide or a tour company must be professional, knowledgeable and has background to the tourism industry in order for them to be credible in making a tourism package that will satisfy and attract a lot of tourist and customers.

Attitudes Towards Making Faith Tourism Packages

The third FGD question was, "what religious attitude a travel agent must show if he or she has a client requesting for a faith tour package? Is this attitude observed in the proposed package?" Patience, considerate, hospitable, understanding, etc. were the major attitudes that was mentioned through the discussion that a tour guide/ tour company. This attitudes mentioned were similar in

the study of Chan and Tay (2016) regarding tour operators' perspectives on responsible tourism practices. It must be added based on the skills discussed previously that tour operator employees also must possess the same attitudes because there are a lot of unexpected events that might happen during the tour and also in booking a tour that is why they need to reflect these attitudes in order to make their service successful. The researchers would like to suggest one significant attitude a tour operator must have in coming up with a Faith Tourism tour package, that attitude is, Prayerful.

Opportunities of Faith Tourism

The fourth FGD question was, "what are the opportunities and how will Cavite tourism benefit if Faith tourism will be promoted in the province?". The shared opportunities in the FGD clearly showed the actual meaning of one of the concepts in the definition of terms about under SWOT, which is opportunities. Wijnmalen (2007) described "opportunities" as future positive results and indeed, the enumerated opportunities are positive results in the future. Speaking of the future, one of the opportunities that was discussed is the place itself. This package is perfectly suitable to the city of Tagaytay because they used the strength of the city itself which is the cold weather that can be used as an advantage to make the tour hassle free. Tagaytay is a truly a very perfect place for the Faith Tourism Package because the city has a lot of existing historical churches which can be also considered as another opportunity.

Benefits of Faith Tourism

The second part of the fourth FGD question was, "what are the opportunities and how will Cavite tourism benefit if Faith tourism will be promoted in the province?". The shared benefits in the FGD clearly showed the actual meaning of one of the concepts in the definition of terms about under SWOT. Wijnmalen (2007) said that opportunities and benefits exist side by side where he described "benefits" as positive results while "opportunities" as future positive results and indeed, the enumerated benefits are positive results in the proposed Faith Tourism tour package. All types of Tourism are beneficial according to its unique purpose, like cultural tourism while will be beneficial to the culture being visited, medical tourism for the promotion of health, etc. What's notable from the interaction in this portion is that most of the benefits of faith tourism discussed pertain to the development benefits of tourism in Tagaytay City. It is possible that this package might be considered by clients, specifically the faithful, because of its affordability and fair itineraries and when this happen this may help boost the competitiveness of tourism in Tagaytay City.

Over-All Perception of the Tour Product Based on TTCI 2017

The fifth FGD question was, "are the inclusions, activities, etc. contained in the proposed Tagaytay Faith-tour package competitive enough based on the TTCI below that will generate a positive approval to travel agents to sell or its clients to buy the product? Why and why not?". Everyone in the FGD agreed that the proposed tour package is competitive. Overall this proposed faith tourism package is a potential model because it is not just affordable but also the package services and itineraries is enough to meet the satisfaction of every tourist. Additionally, the different tour operators suggested for some inclusions and suggestions to the proposed tour package, such as, the inclusion of travel insurance and souvenirs. The suggestion regarding souvenirs by the participants is in accordance with Olsen and Timothy (2006) tourism study in India, where the one of the findings was the entire tourism industry has grown up around this [Faith Tourism] form of

travel, complete with specialized travel agencies, particular types of accommodation, specific kinds of eating places, an array of gift and souvenir shops specializing in religious paraphernalia.

Competitiveness of Tagaytay City

The competitiveness of Tagaytay City was appraised according to the Travel and Tourism Competitive Index (TTCI) 2017 using SWOT analysis. Blokdyk (2018) himself said that SWOT analysis can be used as a practical tool for self-assessment, thus a self-assessment was made between Tagaytay City and TTCI 2017 to determine its competitiveness. On the General setting, business in Tagaytay City is thriving through the continuous establishment of several malls, restaurant, parks, recreational sites, hotel renovations. On Travel and Tourism policies, travel and tourism programs in Tagaytay City are prioritized because these are considered two of the major income sources of the city. On infrastructure, Tagaytay has everything needed in the tourism and hospitality industry despite the absence of an airport, Tagaytay City can be reached by helicopters, that's why it is appraised as "opportunities". Lastly, on Resources, the land is suited for crops such as coffee, pineapple, corn, banana, sweet potatoes, coconuts, palay and vegetables.

Is Tagaytay City in the province of Cavite, Philippines, competitive in the tourism and hospitality industry? Can it be marketed as a Faith Tour destination? The study revealed that it is truly indeed. In fact, even the present 2019 Mayor Dr. Agnes Tolentino believed the diverse tourism potential of the city that why she came up with a unique tag-line for Tagaytay City: A place where you can 'Dine, Stay, Play and Pray'.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

Faith Tourism and any form of tourism can therefore be studied by the active Millennial Age in both Quantitative and Qualitative ways. The proposed faith tourism tour package presented in the study that reflects Dr. Sampad Kumar Swain's basic components is competitive. Specifically, the tourist attractions in the itinerary were all associated with Faith Tourism, Tagaytay City is a place where one can play, eat, sleep and pray, the Transportation in the itinerary is appropriate to Faith Tourism, the accommodations in the itinerary has religious settings, and the activities in the tour package will surely provide a meaningful religious experience. Dr. Swain is correct in saying that tourist destinations and tourists' attractions are stable elements while Tourist activities, Meals and accommodations, Transportations are unstable elements in a tour package. Lastly, on the over-all perception of the tour product based on TTCI 2017, all FGD participants confirmed the proposed tour package as competitive. And using SWOT analysis as a tool for assessment, Tagaytay City is "strongly" competitive based on the TTCI 2017 components. The competitiveness of Tagaytay City is indeed seen from the 2016 latest Cavite ecological profile report because Tagaytay City has the most tourist arrivals in the Province of Cavite.

Most of the respondents of the survey questionnaire belong to the group of 18 to 27 age interval, male, single, and belonging to college level, thus the study recommends more involvement of other respondents especially the women, those belonging to other age group, marital status and educational attainment by providing these respondents with affordable travel opportunities. And based on the proposed Faith Tourism Tour package in Tagaytay City, this tour package is not an expensive trip.

On the perception of the proposed faith tourism tour package whether it reflects Dr. Sampad Kumar Swain's five basic components, three-day seminar workshop maybe conducted with the objective of coming up with a common itinerary with Tourist Attractions, Tourist Destination, Transportation, Meals and accommodation, and Tourist activities. Included in this three-day workshop is an actual travel using the itinerary made. Specifically, the following may be recommended from each components: first, For the stable components, more promotional strategies so that the tourist destinations will become clearly the star of the tour package, as well as, the tourist attractions on the proposed tour package can be competitive with other forms of tourism (cultural, adventure, etc.); for the unstable components, the transportation safety and conduciveness to travel must be ensured through the inclusion of a travel insurance, the meals and accommodations must be clearly seen and explained by adding these information in detail on the brochure, and the tour operator help explain that the activities can be participated by tourists belonging to other faith, not for profit but to witness a new religious experience and enjoyment.

Faith Tourism is not just about pilgrimage, thus on the knowledge, skills and attitude in making Faith Tourism Itineraries, a further study maybe proposed to determine the level of understanding, level of awareness and level of familiarity on this specific kind of tourism for enrichment of knowledge, improvement of skills and enhancement of attitude. As an overall recommendation, the study recommends to explore other Quantitative and Qualitative approaches such as Case Studies, Phenomenological studies or comparative studies of Faith Tourism with other types of tourism. The study may also be administered to priests and other religious communities so that they can best promote this type of tourism to the faithful under their care. Lastly, the researchers highly recommend and giving unconditional permission to use the Faith Tourism Tour Package in Tagaytay City. This Faith-tour itinerary may serve as guide, most especially for local tourism's additional tourism revenue, religious sector's pilgrimage tours, education sector's fieldtrips, including tour operators or travel agencies' travel options and promotions. The researchers hope that the tour package will not only be observed during holy week, but all year round.

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